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How Can Law Be Robust in the Face of Heightened Societal Turbulence?

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ABSTRACT

Taking its cue from the growing frequency of disruptive crises, new research argues that crisis-induced turbulence calls for robust governance based on adaptation and innovation. While law plays a key role in the effort of governments to govern robustly, the robustness of law has received scant regard. To compensate for this gap, this article defines robust legality, analyzes its conditions of emergence, reflects on the different forms it might take, and considers the prospects for advancing robust legal regulation. Studying legal robustness enables public management researchers and practitioners to better understand the role of law in times of heightened societal turbulence.

1 | Introduction

The public sector in liberal democracies is not merely supposed to routinely regulate society and the economy and deliver key public services on a day-to-day basis; it is also responsible for safeguarding core public functions, purposes, and values, such as the provision of critical infrastructure, public health and safety, social and political cohesion, the rule of law, and liberal democracy. In stable times with smooth societal reproduction characterized by an absence of major crises and disruptive events, there are few challenges to the ability of public officials to sustain these fundamental public commitments. But when the level of societal turbulence suddenly rises, doing so becomes much more difficult (Ansell and Trondal 2018). This problem appears to be increasingly acute, as we are currently facing heightening levels of crisis-induced turbulence, defined as the presence of surprising, disturbing, and unpredictably changing social, economic, and political dynamics (Ansell et al. 2024).

Recent decades have seen a mushrooming of disruptive crises, such as the financial crisis, the refugee crisis, Brexit, the

Russo–Ukrainian War, the energy crisis, the inflation crisis, Russian hybrid warfare, the climate crisis, the biodiversity crisis, and so forth, which tend to overlap and exacerbate each other, producing what is now referred to as a poly-crisis (Zeitlin et al. 2019). Both the entangled crises themselves and the various forms of crisis management tend to augment the level of societal turbulence characterized by the complex and dislocating interaction between events, developments, and demands. The COVID-19 pandemic offers a case in point: Both the exponentially growing number of infected citizens and the attempts to slow down the accelerating infection rate and prevent the collapse of the healthcare system through more or less draconian lockdowns contributed to unpredictable health, economic, social, and political dynamics that, in turn, fostered a spate of changing demands for compensation and intervention.

The rising level of societal turbulence challenges the ability of government to uphold fundamental public functions, purposes, and values, and thus calls for robust governance that can help to safeguard key public commitments by means of flexible adaptation and proactive innovation of public policies, regulations,

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and services (Capano and Woo 2018; Howlett et al. 2018; Ansell et al. 2021, 2024). The robust governance concept provides us with a new and pertinent understanding of how to change what must be changed while preserving what should be preserved. The implicit “dynamic conservatism” aimed at changing to preserve (Ansell et al. 2015) has thus far been studied mainly from political, administrative, and democratic perspectives (Ansell and Sørensen 2023; Ansell et al. 2021; Carstensen et al. 2023; Sørensen and Warren 2024). The legal aspects of robust governance pertaining to how the constitutional foundations of society, different types of legislation, and the steady stream of legally binding public regulations, administrative orders, executive decrees, and so forth can help to safeguard key public goals and ambitions in times of societal turbulence have received scant attention. This is unfortunate since legal flexibility is key to governance robustness. It is impossible to uphold key public functions, purposes, and values in the face of unexpected perturbations without legal flexibility facilitating adaptation and innovation. Balancing legal flexibility with continuing governance stability aiming to preserve key legal standards and public ambitions is the essence of robust governance and helps to avoid legal changes being perceived or experienced as perpetually destabilizing, disruptive, and unfair (see Craig et al. 2017; DeCaro et al. 2017). To compensate for the relative neglect of the legal aspects of robust governance, this conceptual article defines robust legality, analyzes its conditions of emergence, reflects on its different forms, and considers the prospects for advancing the robustness of legal regulation.

To further motivate the need for legal robustness, let us briefly consider the pinch that the Danish government found itself in during the pandemic. In June 2020, it was discovered that many of the 17 million minks in Denmark were infected with a new variant of the COVID-19 virus. While the danger of the new variant was disputed, Danish health authorities told the government that continued mink breeding posed a significant risk to public health as it created a breeding ground for new mutations of the COVID-19 virus that could undermine the effectiveness of new vaccines. The director of the Danish health authorities proclaimed that in a worst-case scenario Denmark risked potentially becoming a new Wuhan. The government was terrified and proposed the culling of all minks in Denmark but lacked a legal foundation for that decision since the detailed regulations in the Pandemic Act only allowed the culling of minks up to a distance of 7.8 km from an outbreak. To avoid the risk of authoritarianism, the Danish constitution does not allow the government to declare a state of emergency, send home the parliament and govern by decree. Hence, the government was stuck between a stone and a hard place, and it ended up calling for the culling of all minks through a public intervention that was only legalized a few weeks later by the passing of a new law in parliament. It was a major political scandal that could have been avoided if the legal room for maneuvering had been wider and thus if the legal framework had been more robust in these matters of combining flexibility with stability. This Danish example from the pandemic is neither arbitrary nor lone standing but an example of a wider and varied set of cases demonstrating the need for legal flexibility when seeking to uphold key public objectives in the face of societal turbulence (see Gerard 2009; Biber and Eagle 2015; Craig et al. 2017; Gyory 2024).

On this background, the research question guiding this article is: *In times of turbulence, how can constitutional law, legislation and legal regulations contribute to upholding key public functions, purposes, and values, such as critical infrastructure, public health and safety, socio-political cohesion, the rule of law, and liberal democracy?* Instead of a technical legal perspective, this question is answered from a public governance perspective that views constitutional law, legislation and legal regulations as “tools of government” (Salamon 2002). Our research design combines theoretical review with empirical illustration and prospective analysis. Our intention was to critically analyze and examine main ideas and relationships around the issue of robust legality by conducting an integrative review (Snyder 2019). This entailed mapping legal and public administration literatures for relevant theoretical debates on robust legality, governance adaptation, legal flexibility, etc. We started with handbooks and highly referenced publications in the field as a starting point for identifying key works that allowed us to branch out and identify further theoretical works on the issue of robust legality. Important discussions of robust normativity (see Plunkett 2019) and norm robustness (see Deitelhoff and Zimmermann 2020) were excluded from our study because they are more focused on identifying authoritative norms and protecting them against contestation than on flexibly adapting and proactively innovating legal regulation to maintain overall goals.

The paper is structured as follows. The first section defines the central concepts of societal turbulence and robust governance before branching out to define robust legality as an important sub-category of robust governance alongside robust politics, robust policy, robust administration and robust democracy. The second section discusses how robust legality is hampered and/or enabled by “formal law,” “substantive law,” and “reflexive law,” and it argues in favor of using hybrid combinations of these different types of law. The third section provides an overview of different forms of robust legality that adapt and innovate legislation and legal regulations at different levels while aiming to find a way between the Scylla of the state of emergency that readily abolishes the legal protection of the rule of law and citizen rights and the Charybdis of rigid insistence on the letter of relatively detailed laws. The fourth section reflects on how, in the future, constitutional law, legislation and legal regulations can become more amenable to adaptation and innovation to meet the rising demands for robust legality in times of crisis-induced turbulence. The conclusion summarizes the argument and points to the need for future studies of the legal aspect of robust governance.

2 | Towards a Concept of Robust Legality

Max Weber (1994) famously claimed that *legal-rational authority* is not only empirically predominant in modern societies but also morally preferable to both *traditional authority* resting on sacred beliefs, inherited customs and unquestioned dogmas and *charismatic authority* resting on devotion to the specific and exceptional sanctity, heroism, or exemplary character of an individual ruler. Legal rules prepared by meritocratically appointed civil servants who are both authorized and bound by law and subsequently endorsed by elected politicians in the wake of reasoned debate have a strong legitimacy that obliges people

to follow them. Legal-rational authority forms the basis of the public bureaucracy, where both political and administrative decisions are based on the rule of law, defined as a durable system of constitutional laws, legislation and legal regulations that are sufficiently clear, stable, and evenly applied to generate legal predictability that allows citizens to foresee the potential legal outcomes of an action. The stable provision of public service and societal regulation based on stable laws and regulations is a fundamental tenet of bureaucracy in liberal democracies, which therefore works best in dull and uneventful times characterized by constant but predictable change and the absence of a major crisis (Drucker 1993).

Today, the relatively stable postwar period of bureaucratic rule in Western Countries, which was premised on steady economic growth, societal consensus, and the Pax Americana, seems to have ended. Economic globalization, technological innovation, political polarization, and a growing number of disruptive crises are all contributing to a heightened level of turbulence. Coming from the Latin *turbulentia*, meaning perturbation, trouble, and irregularity, the concept of “*turbulence*” has long been used to describe disorderly movements within crowds of animals, children, or troops. The turbulence concept gained popularity in fluid mechanics, where it is used to characterize flows that are eddying rather than laminar (e.g., cloud movement, river currents, fire whirls) (Schmitt 2017). In the social sciences, references to turbulence appeared in the mid-1960s (Easton 1965; Emery and Trist 1965, 1973; Popper 1966). Waldo (1971) observed how public administration confronts an increasingly turbulent environment associated with emerging anti-materialistic revolts stressing the destruction of the biosphere, inner-city decay, and declining quality of life. In line with this, Drucker (1993) claimed that society was entering a new era marked by radical structural shifts that change the critical parameters of the world and call for political and administrative responses. Whereas Waldo and Drucker analyzed national level turbulence, Rosenau studied how turbulence at the international and global levels unsettles the structures and processes that normally sustain world politics (Rosenau 1966, 1995). More recently, governance research has aimed to understand how dynamic interactive changes challenge public governance, defined as the formulation and achievement of common goals (Ansell and Trondal 2018; Nolte et al. 2020; Zhong et al. 2023). Here, turbulence is described as “situations where events, demands, and support interact and change in highly variable, inconsistent, unexpected or unpredictable ways” (Ansell and Trondal 2018, 1).

The concept of “societal turbulence,” defined as the sudden emergence of unpredictable and changing dynamics, adds a temporal dimension to the complex and “wicked” problems facing public governance systems (Rittel and Webber 1973). Public officials are not merely facing problems characterized by cognitive and political complexity, but also problems that are mutating due to the contingent interaction of new events, developments, and demands (Ansell et al. 2024).

Societal turbulence undermines the ability of public officials to achieve key public goals and ambitions. In that sense, the turbulence concept overlaps with the concept of crisis (Ansell et al. 2024). Despite their similarities, however, the two concepts are different. While a crisis tends to be relatively short-lived,

caused by a single dislocating event, and posing a threat to the survival of entire systems, turbulence tends to be more enduring, caused by a set of interacting events, and something we can live with despite its disruptive character. Furthermore, crises are seen as exceptional while turbulence is rapidly becoming normalcy. The two concepts are different but also intrinsically related: a crisis may spur turbulence due to spill-over effects and the unintended negative effects of the attempts to manage them, and turbulence may trigger a crisis due to the self-sustaining accumulation of disparate developments, events, and demands, forming a perfect storm exacerbated by maladaptive public responses (Emery and Trist 1965; Ansell and Trondal 2018).

Public bureaucracy can normally deal well with low levels of societal turbulence, but when the turbulence levels suddenly spike, the rigid insistence on compliance with extant laws, rules, regulations, norms and routines comes under pressure. New research argues that rising levels of societal turbulence call for “*robust governance*” (Capano and Woo 2017, 2018; Ansell et al. 2024). The concept of robustness is discussed in different scientific disciplines and can be defined generically as the ability of a particular unit to maintain a particular function, purpose, or value in a turbulent environment by means of flexible adaptation and/or proactive innovation (Jen 2005). There has been growing interest in the social sciences in studying robustness in social systems theory (Anderies et al. 2004; Anderies and Janssen 2013), environmental planning (Simonovic and Arunkumar 2016), disaster management (Velasquez et al. 2020), and public policy (Ferraro et al. 2015; Howlett et al. 2018). The core of the arguments in this literature is that robustness is achieved by being responsive, open, and adaptive in the face of emerging challenges and unanticipated conditions caused by social, spatial, and temporal variability. More recently, discussions of political robustness have emphasized the need to develop robust responses to societal turbulence that are effective and legitimate (Ansell and Sørensen 2023). Research on policy robustness stresses the need for designed-in diversity, modularity and redundancy (Capano and Woo 2018). Similarly, research on robust democracy looks at the ability of the political system to transform itself in ways that enable it to serve its core democratic functions in the face of disruptive political demands and events (Sørensen and Warren 2024). Building on these discussions, we define robust governance as the ability to uphold key public functions, goals and values in the face of heightened societal turbulence through the formulation and implementation of effective and legitimate governance responses that flexibly adapt and proactively innovate the *modus operandi* of the public sector (Ansell et al. 2023, 2024). The implicit focus on the need “to change to preserve” (Ansell et al. 2015) marks a clear difference between our concept of robustness and the traditional static notion of resilience that aims to “bounce back” and restore the status quo ante (Aldunce et al. 2014). In line with new theories of dynamic resilience (Capano and Woo 2018), our notion of robustness promotes governance that seeks to “bounce forward” through adaptation and innovation.

While there are numerous studies of what makes democracy robust in the face of changing conditions and demands (Layman 2016; Sørensen and Torfing 2019; Bednar 2021; Sørensen and Warren 2024), robustness is not a central theme in legal studies despite the recent focus on the role of law in

adaptive governance (Craig et al. 2017; Cosens et al. 2017, 2020). Nevertheless, scholars have asked the question: How can legal norms be robust in the sense of continuing to be relevant and effective in times when they are tested by emergencies, rapid change and disruptive dynamics (Brunnée and Toope 2019; McLean et al. 2021; Soininen et al. 2023)? The rule of law is supposed to protect citizens from arbitrary and unpredictable treatment, but it comes under pressure when governments face sudden emergencies and disruptive irregularities or when political leaders want to transform society through radical reforms. Such situations raise questions concerning whether and how the rule of law will be upheld in some form or another (see Sypnowich 1999). Branching out from the generic definition of robustness and the radial definition of robust governance, we propose defining “robust legality” as the construction of a flexible combination of legal tools, such as enablement laws, conditional exemptions, legal restrictions, regulatory advice, and post hoc control and accountability mechanisms, that helps to uphold the critical infrastructures, public health and safety, socio-political cohesion, the rule of law and the broad societal norms of liberal democracy during spells of heightened turbulence. Robust legality is needed when crisis-induced turbulence presses governments to adapt and innovate how they regulate society and are possibly tempted to act swiftly and self-willed and use overly drastic and coercive measures to counter an emergency situation. The overarching goal of legal robustness is to facilitate effective and legitimate governance in the face of unpredictable dynamics through a contingent, pragmatic and hybrid combination of different types of law and different legal models. While this definition of robust legality is inspired by public administration discussions of robust governance (Ansell et al. 2024), it resonates well with ideas from legal studies that define “robust law” as a legal system that incorporates checks and balances to resist turbulence due to unforeseen changes in the environment it constitutes and regulates (Hildebrandt 2021).

At its core, the robust governance concept focuses on how the form and content of governance must be changed to uphold a particular governance function. The same applies to the concept of robust legality, where the key functions, purposes, and values inherent to constitutional law and the social and political order of society are sought to be maintained through the adaptation and innovation of enabling laws, legislation and legal regulations. While enabling laws, such as emergency laws, may supplement constitutional law and its emergency and exception clauses by granting power and authority to specific agencies, legislation and legal regulations are placed further down the judicial hierarchy, but may still contribute to legal robustness.

3 | How Do Different Types of Law Provide the Conditions of Emergence for Robust Legality?

When the public sector faces a heightened level of societal turbulence, it must robustly change its *modus operandi* to uphold core public functions, purposes, and values. It is not only the legal framework for the regulatory tools administered by public managers and for the public services delivered by frontline personnel that must be changed to uphold key public commitments, but also the legal framework that prompts and prohibits social, political, and economic action. The need to change the

legal parameters of society during spells of heightened turbulence raises pertinent questions about how to make room for legal adaptation and innovation in response to turbulence, and how different types of law inherent to the existing legal framework enable a flexible adjustment and proactive innovation of statutory law, administrative agency law, and case law.

Creating space to adapt existing laws and rules or to introduce new ones in response to unforeseen, changing and troubling circumstances is key to ensuring robust legality. As noted by Helms (2016), the capacity to carry out adaptive and innovative legal reforms is conditioned by existing institutions, including legal frameworks that make it more or less imperative and more and less easy to transform legal norms and regulations. The need for legal adaptation and innovation depends on the legal legacy inherent to the complex and interconnected landscape of policies that shape political life and public governance. The legal parameters of such a “policyscape” (Mettler 2016) may, in some instances, be relatively effective and up to date, while in other instances, it is entirely dysfunctional and outdated, thus in need of change. Moreover, the ability to enhance legal flexibility in the face of heightened turbulence without compromising the rule of law depends on a country’s legal baseline. For instance, the United Kingdom has no written constitution, strong one-party governments, and a tradition for delegating substantial power to the administrative state, whereas other countries leave much less discretion to the bureaucracy, must reconcile diverse political interests in coalition governments, and are bound by detailed constitutional principles, thus reducing their capacity for legal flexibility. To further explore the institutional conditions for robust legality, we shall consider the contribution of different styles of law to the promotion of robust legality based on flexible adjustments and proactive innovations.

Researchers in the field of comparative law distinguish between different *legal cultures*, defined as the social practices of a legal community; different *legal paradigms*, defined as the common understanding of the nature, sources, interpretation, and legitimacy of law within the legal profession; and different *legal doctrines*, defined as the legitimizing narrative descriptions, classifications, and systematizations of law (Van Hoecke and Warrington 1998; Cotterrell 2019). Here, we focus on something different; namely, the different *types of law* that are found within a legal system. Rather than juxtaposing statutory and customary law, we are instead interested in how different forms of law and legal regulations aim to regulate behavior through the formation of legally binding norms. As such, we follow Teubner (1983) in distinguishing between three types of law: (1) “formal law” that provides detailed legal instruction; (2) “substantive law” that states legal goals, intentions, and perhaps a few general strategies and tools for goal attainment; and (3) “reflexive law” that installs, defines, and guides democratic self-regulatory mechanisms for legal adjudication. While all three types of law are “substantive” in the sense of pursuing substantive political and normative goals, they differ in how they pursue these goals. In much the same way as EU regulations, formal law offers binding and detailed legal provisions, whereas substantive law, in much the same way as EU directives, specifies a certain goal that must be achieved but leaves the methods for goal attainment to administrative discretion. By contrast, reflexive law is more focused on providing a framework for cross-boundary interaction

between distributed actors engaged in self-regulated problem solving and goal attainment.

Over time, the three types of law have evolved in both theory and practice through a critical appraisal of the previous ones. While *formal law* was originally designed to protect individual autonomy, support the operation of private markets, and defend the integrity of the political system, it was not intended as a tool for intervening in society in the pursuit of normative-political agendas. Honoring the rule of law, it provided detailed legal prescriptions for how to provide rudimentary public services and social benefits for citizens and how to regulate society and the economy. After World War II, there was a new political impetus and an optimistic belief in the possibility of creating a socially just society by means of *substantive law* aimed at intervening in the social and economic dynamics of society and offering welfare services and benefits to different target groups. Substantive law is driven by social purpose rather than formal legal rationality. It aims to stipulate some broad goals and tools and leaves the making of further rules to public officials, while frontline staff are charged with processing individual cases based on professional discretion. More recently, the criticism of the top-down character of substantive law and the discretionary power of public officials and caseworkers—together with growing demands for a more involving approach to making and applying binding legal decisions—has led to the emergence of *reflexive law*, which aims to create procedures for how and when different actors should interact to produce the legal governance of functionally differentiated societies. While the different types of law have developed successively as part of a learning process, they all tend to co-exist in shifting combinations across political systems and policy areas. Our claim is that the different types of law provide different possibilities for robust legality and that their combination may also be highly conducive to an adaptive and innovative application of legal regulation to shifting situations and needs. Let us now more thoroughly examine the three types of law in turn.

Formal law is both formal and rational (Teubner 1983). Based on legal norms and principles and a set of deductive logics, it prescribes how members of society must behave, providing clear, general, and stable legal prescriptions that rule particular behaviors in and out (Waldron 2020). Formal law has direct implications for all members of society by prompting and prohibiting certain actions while laying down a set of individual rights. It also has some indirect implications by defining and regulating the decisions made by public officials and frontline personnel. Public law aims to determine how society and the economy should be regulated and what kind of public services should be provided when and how. It aims to reduce the impact of administrative discretion by providing detailed instructions for public regulation and service provision. The prescriptions concerning the content of administrative decisions are often accompanied by procedural prescriptions for when and how public authorities should intervene in social and economic life and respond to citizen requests. The procedural prescriptions may also determine the right to appeal.

The instructional clarity and detail of formal law facilitate the enforcement of the law by public authorities, which helps to secure the rule of law (Waldron 2020). However, Baldwin (1990)

argues that “rules don’t work,” particularly in the context of complex environments. Another problem is that formal law and its large number of detailed rules and regulations easily become outdated and come to appear excessively rigid in the face of growing societal turbulence (DeCaro et al. 2017). In defense of formal law, Waldron (2020) claims that prescriptive law may deal with extraordinary situations of crisis and societal turmoil, either by relying on a spirit of flexibility and circumstantial sensitivity, or by laying down legal rules in advance for how to deal with emergencies. However, it is unclear how to resolve the potential conflict between the spirit of flexibility and the demand for clear and predictable legal prescriptions, and it is difficult to see how rules for dealing with unpredictable future events can be designed in advance without reducing these rules to a set of possible legal exemptions and procedures for who does what.

Substantive law is infused with social purpose, as it aims to compensate for market inadequacies and to modify the behaviors of private market actors. Associated with the rise of the social welfare state, it has little faith in the efficiency and effectiveness of clear, general, and formal rules that prescribe the same uniform solutions across different individual cases. As such, it often makes use of framework laws that lay down general principles and obligations, leaving the determination of the specific measures to be taken to competent authorities and their professionally trained staff so as to realize such obligations (Knuth and Vidar 2011, 30). Hence, instead of providing detailed rules for how to deal with different incidents, demands, and cases, substantive law stipulates some broad policy objectives, key principles, and recommended tools. It then expects public managers and frontline staff to use their competences and discretionary powers to determine how best to achieve the stipulated objectives. To illustrate, substantive law may regulate primary education by merely defining the overall objectives of public schools, specifying some basic governance principles, and determining a set of administrative requirements. Local and regional public authorities then use the national framework to establish and operate public schools that serve the overall purpose and respect key principles and requirements while adapting them to local conditions and preferences.

Substantive law tends to be more adaptive and allows for more legal innovation than formal law because it allows for discretionary professional decisions about how particular overall goals can be achieved in a particular context and at a particular point in time. Hence, while the general purposes and ambitions remain the same, there is considerable room for flexibility with respect to using shifting combinations of different tools and adapting the implementation of basic normative principles to changing conditions on the ground (McDonald and McCormack 2021). Nonetheless, substantive law is very top-down and linear, as it builds on the bureaucratic chain of command running from political legislators, via executive managers, to frontline staff; and since the discretion of the latter is not only constrained by a rigid set of goals, principles, and recommended tools, it may also be subjected to more specific administrative rules and standards. As such, framework law sometimes falls short of providing robust solutions to rapidly changing conditions. To remedy this problem, Arnold and Gunderson (2013) propose a new adaptive law framework based on four key features: (1) adaptive goals aiming for multiple forms of resilience; (2) a polycentric,

multimodal, and multiscale adaptive system structure; (3) methods of adaptation and context-regarding flexibility; and (4) iterative processes with both feedback loops and accountability mechanisms. The emphasis on polycentric, context-sensitive adaptation of both goals and tools based on procedures for feedback and learning points in the direction of reflexive law.

Reflexive law is a more recent and underdeveloped type of law emerging in response to calls for a more involving, coordinated, and adaptive legal adjudication that breaks with the deductive linearity of formal law and the political linearity of substantive law. Citing the work on responsive law of Nonet and Selznick (1978), which emphasizes the role of participation, and the work on evolutionary law of Luhmann (1970) and Habermas (1981), which stresses the role of legal self-reflection, Teubner (1983) defines reflexive law as a self-regulating legal system that provides reflexive structures and procedures that enable a group of actors to engage in collaborative legal coordination that takes into account externalities based on joint context-dependent interpretations. Reflexive law relies on procedural norms that regulate processes, organization, and the distribution of competences. It provides methods of coordination and integration of relevant and affected organizations within functionally differentiated societies, and it is legitimized by the desirability of self-regulated coordination based on collaboration. To illustrate, new Danish statutory sick leave provisions neither provide detailed legal rules nor broad social purposes, instead specifying when and how long-term ill laborers should interact with their general practitioner, employer, and trade union to find a solution allowing them to return to work (Jacobi 2013).

Legal adjudication based on reflexivity allows a group of actors with different roles and competences to deal with externalities arising from turbulence based on a joint interpretation of their form, nature, and urgency that is shaped by the system in which they operate. The response of the actors to turbulent events, developments, and demands is based on coordination and integration. In addition, since it is dictated by neither formal rules nor overriding political-normative concerns, it can be flexible and innovative, depending on the actors' joint assessment. To illustrate, local public managers, school heads, and parent representatives in the local school board may jointly deliberate about how to re-open local schools in a safe and responsible manner after the government has lifted the COVID-induced lockdown. They may be bound by a common commitment to open the local schools in accordance with national health regulations to provide opportunities for learning and social well-being, and procedures for coordinating and integrating different views and concerns may help to provide adaptive and innovative solutions. However, when adapting and innovating local solutions to shifting conditions, the actors may risk losing sight of the core functions, purposes, and values (unless they are repeatedly communicated and restated or deeply ingrained in the identity of the actors).

In sum, while formal law with its preference for the legal enforcement of precise and detailed rules provides limited scope for robust governance based on flexible adaptation and proactive innovation, substantive law significantly extends this scope by creating space for local and regional discretion based on top-down goal formulation. Reflexive law tends to further expand

the scope for robust governance by enabling relevant and affected actors to reflect on the need for and form of changes in response to externalities. That said, the analysis presented above reveals positive and negative impacts on the robust legality of all three types of law. This suggests that a hybrid combination of all three types of law may be conducive to obtaining robust legality (see also Craig et al. 2017). Hybridity allows public officials to mix-and-match different types of law depending on context and situation and enhances the ability to adapt and innovate public solutions by flexibly shifting the balance between different types of law to match changing circumstances (Nõmmik et al. 2024). Country-specific legal cultures, paradigms and doctrines may tie public officials to a particular type of law or give rise to entrenched legal hybrids, but the legal parameters can be changed by political coalitions facing pressures from crisis-induced turbulence. Ideally, the changes aimed for by the policy entrepreneurs should be based on a recognition of the comparative advantages of the different types of law.

Reflexive law is strong on collaborative adaptation and innovation but risks losing sight of the core public functions, purposes, and values to be upheld in turbulent situations. By contrast, substantive law is firmly anchored in core public objectives and provides space for local adaptation that may be based on reflexive law that reaps the fruits of collaborative interaction. Formal law tends to act as a barrier to the local adaptation and innovation of legal norms and regulations in response to societal turbulence, but the speed of centralized rulemaking may provide an important complement to the slowness of collaborative coordination and integration in reflexive law, and it may provide key guidelines for the local adaptation of centrally defined public purposes. As such, constructive hybridization—deliberately mixing and matching different types of law in shifting combinations—may expand the scope for robust legality by creating synergies and exploiting complementarities (Nõmmik et al. 2024; Røiseland et al. 2024). So far, legal hybridity has primarily been discussed in relation to countries trying to straddle different legal traditions (Castellucci 2012; Yilmaz 2022), but it is also relevant for public officials aiming to respond robustly to complex and turbulent problems (Forsyth 2020).

4 | Robust Ways of Adapting and Innovating Legal Regulations

This section provides an overview of different forms of robust legality that adapt and innovate legal regulations at different levels while aiming to find a way between the Scylla of the state of emergency that completely abolishes the rule of law and fundamental citizen rights and the Charybdis of rigid insistence on the letter of the law that prevents robust governance.

Since the very inception of liberal democracies, constitutionalist writers have been preoccupied with the conundrum over how to ensure the security and survival of states and their people in emergency situations without sacrificing liberty. Emergency situations are characterized by shorter or longer periods of intense societal turbulence. Alexander Hamilton, one of the framers of the U.S. constitution, believed that “no constitutional shackles can wisely be imposed on the power to which the care of it is committed” (Rossiter 1961, 153). He based this belief on the—in

our view very realistic—assumption that “it is impossible to foresee or to define the extent and variety of national exigencies, and the correspondent extent and variety of the means, which may be necessary to satisfy them” (Rossiter 1961, 153). In brief, because it is impossible to envisage and therefore define what an emergency could be, it is untenable to design a constitution effectively handling all future threats in a way that simultaneously protects legislative processes and individual liberties. Accordingly, in the event of an emergency situation that threatens the security of a state or its population, governments and legislatures are often bound to find a new way of balancing contradictory concerns over security and liberty.

Inspired by Gross and Aoláin (2006), we examine models for robustly handling highly turbulent emergency situations that span a continuum from extra-legal powers over various accommodation models to a business-as-usual approach. Our examination includes both description and discussion of the robustness of these models, depending on the nature of the emergency.

4.1 | The Extra-Legal Model

This model entails that government officials, in a highly turbulent emergency situation, may transgress or bracket the law when believing such action to be necessary to protect the nation and general public (Gross and Aoláin 2006, 111–13). Given that there is no objective definition of what constitutes an emergency situation, the model is predicated on government officials publicly diagnosing the crisis and acknowledging and justifying their actions. Such public justifications may even include arguments declaring the need to transgress constitutional principles, rules, and norms. Moreover, the model emphasizes the strict requirement for popular *ex post* sanctioning of such extra-legal measures. When an extra-legal measure is adopted, the people must subsequently decide how to respond, either directly through referendum or indirectly via their elected representatives in the legislature. By implication, the extra-legal model does not allow for suspension of the functioning of the legislature or regular electoral processes.

In principle, the extra-legal model may sound like a promising response to spells of crisis-induced turbulence. Indeed, governments are granted exceptional powers, but the public can sanction them easily, because government officials are obliged to acknowledge and justify their actions and are subsequently held to account for them. In practice, however, the extra-legal model is problematic. The measures adopted by the Bush administration following 9/11 included the widespread and illegal surveillance of American citizens, the use of torture when interrogating suspected terrorists (by defining them as non-combatant suspected terrorists), and the transfer of suspected terrorists to extra-legal localities, notably Guantanamo Bay, to avoid national and international legal requirements. Instead of acknowledging and justifying these actions, the Bush administration went to great lengths to cover up their actions. Even if many Americans actually endorsed some of these extra-legal measures, the Bush administration obviously feared the political and legal consequences of openly admitting to them.

Even in the case of the pandemic, holding government officials to account following their transgression of constitutional rules has proven difficult. For instance, following the unconstitutional and unlawful decision to cull all mink in Denmark to curb the mutation and spread of new strains of the COVID-19 virus that may be immune to vaccines, the Danish prime minister and her top advisors explained the decision as a procedural error instead of justifying it as a necessary measure to protect public health in Denmark and abroad. While the government reasoning remains obscure, it seems likely that the government feared the legal and, not least, parliamentary repercussions of admitting to any premeditated constitutional violation. In brief: When breaking constitutional and legal rules for the purpose of upholding national security or even public health, government politicians and officials are reluctant to publicly justify having done so.

Even if a combination of structured procedures and conscientious government officials somehow ensures the justification and accountability of extra-legal action, the extra-legal model for dealing with crisis-induced turbulence clearly holds little in common with robust legality, as it readily abandons what robust legality aims to maintain. The logic of the extra-legal model is that the emergency situation is so grave that it justifies the suspension of some key legal principles, namely the rule of law and basic civil and political liberties, to maintain public health and safety and the socio-political cohesion and unity. Both the implicit trade-off between different public ambitions and the ensuing public and parliamentary resentment linked to the failure of holding government actors responsible for abuse imply that the extra-legal mode has little to offer when it comes to robust governance of societal turbulence.

4.2 | The Accommodation Model and Its Three Versions: Constitutional, Legal, and Interpretive

As the name indicates, the accommodation model aims to accommodate the pressures exerted on the state in times of emergency and societal turbulence. Hence, in a turbulent emergency situation, the legal—and even constitutional—structure, procedures, and rules of a state must be relaxed to some degree to allow for continued adherence to the principle of the rule of law and faithfulness to fundamental liberal democratic values, while providing the state with adequate measures to protect public safety and the socio-political cohesion of society and state (Gross and Aoláin 2006, 9). There are three different versions of the accommodation model—the constitutional, legislative and interpretive—which concurrently aim to maintain normal legal principles and rules as far as possible by means of changing the content of relevant legal regulations to accommodate turbulent events, developments, and demands.

The constitutional accommodation version essentially entails that the constitution elaborately defines all the possible instances of emergency situations and provides the necessary powers to government to handle them (Gross and Aoláin 2006, 35–6). The rationale for this version of the accommodation model is to legally regulate exceptional actions within the framework of the constitution while providing the government with the necessary

powers to secure both the security and unity of the state and the fundamental rights of the citizens. Accordingly, the U.S. constitution grants exceptional powers to the president, notably in the case of war (Ferejohn and Pasquino 2004). This clause has been used both in benevolent situations, such as the U.S. engagement in World War II, but also in less benevolent ones, such as the Vietnam War. The constitutions of Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, and Portugal go even further and contain various clauses stipulating executive powers not only in the case of war but also other emergencies. In contrast, countries such as Belgium, Japan, the Nordics, and many others have no emergency clauses in their constitution. There are obviously many historically specific reasons for countries not to have any emergency clauses in their constitution. But a key political and legal argument supporting the reluctance to adopt emergency clauses is the danger inherent in delegating massive powers to the executive to the point where it will exclusively define not only the measures to be taken but also what counts as an emergency allowing for such measures.

The legislative accommodation version entails that the constitutional principles and values are kept intact while some special adjustments are introduced through legislative amendments and modifications into the existing ordinary legal terrain (Gross and Aoláin 2006, 66). It accepts that existing legal rules and regulations do not provide an adequate answer to the disruptive turbulence facing the nation. At the same time, however, it assumes that such answers exist within an adapted and innovated legal framework that does not require radical changes to the existing constitutional-legal structure. This version of the accommodation model appeared to offer a robust handling of the recent pandemic. As demonstrated by Ginsburg and Versteeg (2021), the legislature, courts, mass media, and sub-national governments played a crucial role in the effective handling of the pandemic through legal adjustments. Even if many countries experienced a temporary concentration of executive power, legislatures provided oversight, the courts insisted on the procedural integrity of declarations of emergency, public media acted as watchdogs questioning dubious government actions while calling for legal adjustments and new legislation, and sub-national governments pushed back and substantially influenced how legal regulations were interpreted and implemented. These forces outside the central government were not a hindrance to effective crisis management, but rather a way of increasing effectiveness and providing legitimacy to handling the pandemic in accordance with liberal democratic principles. Governments were forced to respect and uphold core public functions, purposes, and values by changing existing or drafting new legislation while allowing discretionary implementation and accepting the revisions based on feedback from manifold social and political actors. The Danish Epidemic Act offers a case in point: At the outbreak of the pandemic, the government recognized that the existing legislation did not fit the situation and hastened to pass a new Epidemic Act that gave the government stronger executive powers. The new Epidemic Act was subsequently amended in response to criticisms of the implicit weakening of legislative powers.

Finally, *the interpretive version of the accommodation model* implies that existing constitutional and legal rules are interpreted by the judiciary in a manner that grants consideration to whether society is in an exceptional situation and posing a

threat to its security (Gross and Aoláin 2006, 32). Rather than changing the existing constitutional rules, laws, and regulations, they are interpreted differently in order to create space for the executive to have access to the extraordinary powers and legal maneuverability necessary to handle crisis-induced turbulence. In other words, the model of interpretive accommodation applies ordinary rules in times of crisis but changes the scope of such rules by way of emergency-minded interpretation (Gross and Aoláin 2006, 33). The judiciary must therefore carefully base its interpretation of existing legal rules on whether the situation is normal or exceptional—according to their understanding, rather than that of the executive. Based on this assessment, they can alter the balance of the key values underpinning many legal interpretations, notably the balance between security and liberty. In the United States, for instance, the interpretation of regulations pertaining to the powers of law enforcement agencies has varied according to crime rates, thus attuning the balance between crime reduction and civil liberties according to societal needs. The advantage of this model is that the power to define whether a given situation is exceptional and, if so, how existing rules should be re-interpreted rests with the judiciary rather than the executive. This should limit the likelihood of government abuse of emergency situations to amass power to further their own interest. However, one of the problems with the interpretive version of the accommodation model is that it places considerable political power in the hands of the judiciary. Moreover, the judiciary rarely has the knowledge—military, intelligence, or public health expertise—to make interpretations that will enable the most effective handling of a turbulent situation. By implication, they either risk making ineffective interpretations or—to mitigate that risk—uncritically adopt the interpretations requested by the executive power. Above all, the public has nowhere to turn if they do not endorse the judicial re-interpretations of existing law, as most countries have an appointed—not elected—judiciary.

In brief, all three versions of the accommodation model aim to uphold basic legal principles while allowing for adaptive and innovative legal changes aimed at accommodating pressures on public functions, purposes and values emanating from crisis-induced turbulence. In that sense, they can all be seen as viable pathways to robust legality.

4.3 | The Business-as-Usual Model

This model implies that ordinary legal rules and norms continue to be followed without any substantive change in times of heightened turbulence, crisis, and emergency, including wars, terror attacks, natural catastrophes, and famines (Gross and Aoláin 2006, 86–9). As the name suggests, the model thus implies both that the letter of the constitution and laws are strictly adhered to and that they do not change in the face of a crisis. This insistence of the business-as-usual model on legal continuity not only pertains to ordinary constitutional norms but also to how they are interpreted in specific cases. The model assumes that the existing constitution and the legal rules and procedures it supports are complete in the sense that they cover all possible exigencies. New laws and legal regulations can be adopted to tackle exceptional and turbulent situations, but their nature and

FIGURE 1 | Graphical illustration of contingency framework showing how robust legality is produced.

the legislative process leading to their adoption must follow ordinary procedures.

The model resonates well with *Rechtstaat* principles, which are a key tenet of all liberal democracies. Clearly, however, the business-as-usual model will be unable to deliver robust legality, as the space for legal adaptation and innovation is restricted to the formulation of new laws that take time and may meet political opposition. Adhering to the letter of the law precludes flexible adaptation, a frequent way for public officials to respond swiftly and robustly to rising turbulence. Equally obviously, the model will often be unable to secure broadly supported aims of state security and the protection of the life, health, socioeconomic prosperity, and fundamental rights of the citizenry when the level of turbulence spikes. Accordingly, the model has been criticized for being dysfunctional—and even hypocritical—due to its lack of engagement with the difficult choices that must be made between security and liberty in crisis situations (Gross and Aoláin 2006, 10). In brief, this model does not appear to ensure robust legality.

In sum, we find a wide range of legal approaches to handling exceptional and turbulent situations. They range from extra-legal measures inspired by classic *realpolitik*, where it is accepted that the executive decision-makers transgress the constitution and suspend extant law in exceptional situations, via some sophisticated accommodation approaches, to the rather crude business-as-usual model. In general, the former tends to maximize the ability of the executive power to do whatever it finds necessary when societies face emergency and turbulence at the expense of key public functions, purposes, and values, such as upholding the rule of law and civic liberties, while the latter fails to afford the capacity for flexible crisis management to executive decision-makers in a blind belief that the constitution and extant laws are complete and will prove their worth in a crisis situation. In comparison, the different versions of the accommodation model all tend to strike a better balance between the need for adaptation and innovation in the face of crisis-induced turbulence and the endeavor to uphold key public functions, purposes, and values. The accommodation model aims to change in order to preserve and can therefore be seen to offer pathways to robust legality, despite the dangers associated with the constitutional version.

While the accommodation model seems to provide the most robust legal tools in general terms, we should be careful not to assume that one model is able to provide robust solutions for all types of crisis-induced turbulence. Rather, the extra-legal model could be useful in times of war, and the business-as-usual model may be applicable in settling rather unexceptional domestic issues. Yet in many of the in-between cases of crisis-induced turbulence, the different versions of the accommodation model (constitutional, legislative, and interpretive) seem useful. Which one is chosen is likely to depend not only on the nature of the crisis but also—and perhaps more importantly—on the historical tradition and political situation of the country subjected to turbulence.

5 | Meeting Future Demands for Robust Legality

So far, we have shown how reflexive law, perhaps in some combination with substantive and formal law, may enhance robust legality that may be pursued in and through the choice of one of three versions of the accommodation model, although contextual issues pertaining to the nature of crisis and historical and political conditions may activate the extra-legal or business-as-usual model. Figure 1 illustrates this key finding that emphasizes the centrality of reflexive law and the accommodation model in providing robust legality but insists that reflexive law may be combined with formal law and substantive law giving rise to legal hybridity and that the accommodation model in some instances may give way to the extra-legal or business-as-usual model, in both cases depending on context.

The question, however, remains how liberal democracies can become more legally robust in the future by making laws and legal regulations more amenable to adaptation and innovation when necessary for upholding core functions, purposes, and values in times of crisis-induced turbulence. Answering this question is more important than ever given the rising levels of societal turbulence and the increasing frequency, endurance, and global impact of major and minor social, economic, environmental, and political crises that tend to give rise to unpredictable and disruptive dynamics.

Based on empirical observations revealing how extant law has turned out to be quite adaptive in several areas, Cosens et al. (2017) argue that it is not fixed but evolving, responsive, and intentionally reformed. With this positive premise in mind, we must consider how to further advance the robust legality of liberal democracies in the years to come. As suggested earlier in this article, specific attention should be paid to how hybrid combinations of formal, substantial, and reflexive law can support robust legality. Such hybrid combinations must aim to harness the strengths and compensate for the weaknesses of the three different types of law to facilitate a dynamic legal conservatism that changes laws and legal regulations based on adaptation and innovation in response to heightened societal turbulence while maintaining key legal functions, purposes, and values. In brief, formal and some aspects of substantial law (the stipulation of overall goals and purposes) may play an important role in providing a conservative adherence to core public commitments, while some other aspects of substantial law (room for local discretion) and reflexive law seem crucial to the provision of sufficient degrees of flexibility and change.

We have also suggested that the extra-legal and business-as-usual models for tackling emergencies will often be unable to produce robust legality due to their exclusive prioritization of either change or stability. By contrast, there is reason to believe that the different versions of the accommodation model in most, but perhaps not all, situations can help to secure legal stability while allowing for change. The accommodation model seems to be predicated on the mutually conditioning character of stability and change (see Ansell et al. 2023). It points to the importance of building flexibility into the constitution, providing procedures for making legal amendments and for granting discretionary powers to the judiciary. The promise for robust legality lies in the fact that the accommodation models normalize flexibility by seeing societal turbulence as a constitutive feature of legal regulation. This resonates with the idea that such flexibility is not only something that is required in rare and unlikely situations but is a permanent requirement in a world where turbulence is becoming the rule rather than the exception.

Now, to answer the question of what it will take for liberal democracies to build appropriate capacities for advancing the robustness of their respective legal systems, we make three propositions emphasizing the role of individual traits, institutional features, and societal characteristics in conditioning robust legality. While the latter two conditions refer to macro-level contextual conditions, the role of institutional traits refers to the new forms of leadership that must be exercised when organizing for robustness. The first condition for enhancing robust legality involves the development of a different mindset among lawmakers, who often prefer formal law designed for quiet times and either extra-legal or business-as-usual responses when crisis-induced turbulence shakes the foundations of society. This individual preference is nurtured by the hegemony of the traditional paternalistic image of strong leadership that is held among politicians and civil servants, which portrays leaders as willful Machiavellian authorities trusting themselves to cut to the chase when need be (Kane and Patapan 2012; Dalton and Welzel 2014). It is also nurtured by the Weberian assumption that stability and predictability are to be expected, and turbulence is a rare and negligible occurrence (Trubek 2017; Sørensen

and Torfing 2024). However, there are new and different leadership ideas on the rise that consider strong leadership to be the result of a responsive ability to recruit, mobilize, and guide competent, critical, and assertive followers—be they citizens, interest organizations, or public employees—and engage them in a collaborative effort to find ways to solve emerging problems and exploit the opportunities triggered by near-permanent levels of heightened turbulence (Nye 2008; Ansell and Gash 2012; Sørensen 2020; Sørensen et al. 2021; Ansell et al. 2022). In their discussion of how to organize for robustness, Micacchi et al. (2025) point to the need for energizing leaders who mobilize actors to perform according to plans as well as to experiment when necessary while securing feedback that allows them to adjust and change plans. In the field of legal regulation, this kind of leadership draws its strength from a skillful use of hybridity through an extensive use of substantive and reflexive law in its efforts to facilitate a flexible and decentered exploration of what works in rapidly shifting and uncertain contexts. It follows that systematic efforts to proactively train and educate lawmakers are a promising way forward rather than waiting for this new mindset to emerge spontaneously and spread by itself (Sørensen and Torfing 2024). Hence, the cultivation of new individual traits conducive to robust legality must be collectively orchestrated.

A second proposition is to institutionalize procedures for the swift adaptation of existing laws to new situations and the timely innovation of new laws in a fashion that lives up to democratic standards. This endeavor entails supplementing existing democratic procedures on the input side of the political system, such as general elections, referenda, and consultative hearings, with new knowledge interphases that can spur the development of negotiated societal intelligence (Russo and Van Dooren 2024) and new accountability mechanisms that commit those involved in the adaptation and innovation of legal regulations to justify their decisions and actions in response to critical questions from relevant and affected constituencies (Fox 2015; Sørensen and Torfing 2021). Promoting dialogue-based knowledge sharing requires the formation of institutional arenas allowing elected politicians to interact with professional experts and lay actors. Holding decision-makers to account for their ex post justifications of legal crisis management depends on the presence of institutional platforms that provide relevant and affected constituencies with ample opportunities to scrutinize the legal changes made, demand explanations, and raise criticisms. Such platforms come in the shape of a widespread network of participatory spaces, physical meeting places, online discussion boards, and multi-level governance institutions that allow different levels of governance to hold each other to account (Ansell and Gash 2018).

The final proposition lies in direct continuation of the call for stronger institutional mechanisms for holding lawmakers to account for their emergency decisions, but is concerned with creating societal conditions for robust legal governance through the cultivation of critical, competent and assertive citizens (Dalton and Welzel 2014) and the development of traditions for collaborative governance (Ansell and Gash 2008) that facilitate the empowered participation of relevant stakeholders and affected citizens (Fung and Wright 2003), both in the formulation of broad substantive policy goals and the local interpretation and implementation of these goals, and in reflexive lawmaking tailoring

legal regulations to shifting local conditions. Enhanced participation in lawmaking of different kinds will help to establish common ownership of policy goals and create a collective intelligence (Boucher et al. 2023) capable of informing the adaptation and innovation of the attempts to achieve the goals in times of heightened turbulence. It will also strengthen the critical scrutiny of how decision-makers justify legal changes in the face of crisis. Granting the members of society formal rights to take an active part in governing society is far from enough to ensure that citizens are capable of playing their role as co-governors. This calls for a deep-rooted socialization process that begins in the family, in kindergartens, and in schools and institutions of higher education. As documented by Dalton and Welzel (2014), however, the impact of such socialization processes is already underway in most liberal democracies. More must be done to stimulate and exploit this asset in an effort to advance robust legality at a time when we really need it.

6 | Conclusion

We live in turbulent times, and there is a pressing need for more robust forms of governance that strengthen our ability to respond rapidly and flexibly to unpredictable and disruptive events, developments, and demands that problematize public goal achievement and render existing ways of operating irrelevant or insufficient. Given that robust governance largely hinges on robust legality, it is surprising that more attention has not been paid to how laws and legal regulations can contribute to upholding key public functions, purposes, and values, such as the promotion of effective and legitimate governance, in an increasingly volatile environment. To fill this gap, this article has defined a new concept of robust legality and examined how different types of law can facilitate robust legality and how different legal responses to emergency and crisis can help to provide robust legal responses to turbulence.

Our analytical comparison of different types of law reveals a growing capacity for robust legality when we move from formal, via substantive, to reflexive law. However, since all three law types have merits and drawbacks, we find that a constructive hybridity that intentionally combines different types of lawmaking may help to enhance the capacity for robust legality. When it comes to the ways of obtaining robust legality, our comparison of different models of laws identifies a space of accommodation between the extra-legal model, which too readily sacrifices core public functionalities, purposes, and values, versus the business-as-usual model that insists on following the letter of the law, which is praised for an illusory completeness. There are different versions of the accommodation model, and exactly what version to select or what versions to combine depends on contextual factors. Drawing on the accommodation model seems to fit well with most forms of heightened crisis-induced turbulence. However, we should not rule out the possibility of leaning more towards the non-robust extra-legal model in times of radical emergencies or towards the equally non-robust business-as-usual when turbulence is more limited. Again, our recommendation is for public officials to skillfully combine different models of law based on a constructive hybridization that aims to match the particular hybrid model with the actual level

of societal turbulence. In sum, when it comes to fostering robust legality during spells of heightened turbulence, it is not between different models since the accommodation model may benefit from being contingently combined with one of the other models.

Our new concept of robust legality contributes to the new and expanding research on robust governance in turbulent times by highlighting the legal aspects of robust governance (Ansell et al. 2021). Our comparative analysis of the types of law and the legal models for responding to different levels of turbulence provides an initial platform for studies of robust legality. However, despite the importance of taking a first step, this article only scratches the surface of robust legality. We hope that future research can advance the concept and study of robust legality further by doing three things. First, we need further conceptual development and refinement to ensure that we are building on a sound conceptual foundation. Second, we need to further theorize the conditions for and forms of robust legality developing useful taxonomies that can be operationalized to guide empirical research. Finally, empirical studies are needed of how central decision-makers alone or in collaboration with relevant and affected actors manage to design robust legal solutions in turbulent times. Empirical studies should not only examine the conditions for robust legality to emerge and the forms that it might take but also study the impact of robust legality. After all, the key question remains: How can public decision-makers flexibly adapt and proactively innovate laws and legal regulations without sacrificing key legal norms and principles? And how successful are they, really?

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

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